

Entrepreneurial Sustainability and Food Security in Nigeria

Ofilu Jude Ikubor, PhD,¹ Augustine Enemali Amana, PhD,² & Mary Yusuf Abdul, PhD.³

¹*Department of Economics, Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna, Nigeria. Corresponding author. Email: ojikubor@nda.edu.ng*

²*Department of Banking and Finance, Veritas University, Abuja, Nigeria. Email: amanae@veritas.edu.ng*

³*Department of Economics, Confluence University of Science and Technology, Osara, Kogi State, Nigeria. Email: abmary7878@gmail.com*

Abstract:

The formulation of public policy to spur agricultural production in the form of agricultural financing measures resulting in the provision of credit facilities to farmers, the introduction of agricultural banks to cater for the specific financial needs of farmers, and investments in road transportation systems may not have yielded the desired outcome, resulting in food scarcity. This study therefore evaluated the effects of entrepreneurial sustainability on food security in Nigeria from 2001 to 2022 using ARDL model. Data for the study was from secondary sourced, Central Bank Statistical bulletin, World Bank data base and the Food and Agriculture Organization. The study revealed that entrepreneurial sustainability, information and communication technology and food security had positive long run relationship. However, agricultural credit, agricultural development assistance, road transport, regulatory quality and Food Security (LFS) had negative long run relationship. Findings reveal the need for government to support food security, through effective credit support, the development of an infrastructural network that would enhance food production coupled with technological advancement. The study concluded that entrepreneurial sustainability can be achieved through consolidated institutional framework that encompass effective regulatory system in Nigeria.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial sustainability, agricultural credit, information technology, food security.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship is recognized as a crucial catalyst for economic advancement, but it requires a focus on sustainability to ensure long term impact. Entrepreneurial sustainability can be described as those practices that ensure long-term viability and success of businesses. Some of these practices include granting financial assistance to entrepreneurs in the form of agricultural credit, the implementation of agricultural development assistance, the provision of good road transport network, public and private sector investments in information and communication technology and the maintenance of institutional quality on food security in Nigeria (Eze & Nwosu 2022; Ogunyinka and Ekwueme (2022); Adeyemi & Adebayo 2023).

The Nigerian government has implemented various policies and programs to support entrepreneurial activities, such as the Youth Enterprise with Innovation in Nigeria, and the National Enterprise Development Programme (NEDEP). These initiatives aim to enhance the capabilities of entrepreneurs, foster innovation, and promote sustainable business practices. Entrepreneurial ventures, including micro, small and medium-sized agro-allied businesses provide employment to a large segment of the population. However, these enterprises face challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited access to finance, and regulatory hurdles (Akpan et al. 2015; Eze et al. 2017; Akinwale & Adepoju 2020).

Nigeria's agricultural sector, which employs about 70% of the workforce, is vital for achieving food security. However, the sector is plagued by low productivity, poor infrastructure, and the impact of climate change. Efforts to improve food security in Nigeria include initiatives to modernize agriculture, enhance food production, and reduce post-harvest losses. Programs like the Agricultural Transformation Agenda (ATA), and the Green Alternative aim to boost agricultural productivity, improve value chains, and ensure food availability (Adesina & Baidu-Forson 1995, Olagunju 2000; Godfray et al. 2010).

Nigeria, with its large population and abundant natural resources, has the potential for significant economic growth. However, the economy faces challenges such as dependence on oil exports, inadequate infrastructure, and political instability. Entrepreneurship is a catalyst for economic growth as it fosters innovation, creates jobs, and stimulates economic activities. By addressing the barriers to entrepreneurship and supporting sustainable business practices, Nigeria can achieve inclusive economic growth and development (Adebisi and Babatope-Obasa 2004, Beck et al. 2005).

Sustainable entrepreneurial practices can enhance food security by promoting agricultural innovations, reducing food waste, and improving supply chains. In turn, improved food security supports economic growth by ensuring a healthy and productive workforce. Moreover, economic growth provides the resources needed to invest in infrastructure, education, and technology, which are essential for sustaining

entrepreneurship and achieving food security. Therefore, understanding and addressing the interconnectedness of these factors is vital for formulating effective policies and strategies to drive Nigeria's development (Cumming et al. 2016; Eze et al. 2017).

Several governments in Nigeria have formulated and implemented policies to grow the entrepreneurial sector with emphasis on agricultural production. This has led to the formulation of public policy to spur agricultural production in the form of subsidy of fertilizers, provision of credit facilities to farmers, the introduction of agricultural banks to cater for the specific financial needs of farmers, and investments in road transportation systems. However, all these measures embarked upon by the government to improve food security in Nigeria have not yielded the desired results. This situation therefore calls for empirical investigation to evaluate the relationship between entrepreneurial sustainability and food security.

Previous studies linking entrepreneurial sustainability and food security in Nigeria include the works of Eze and Nwosu (2020), Ogunyinka and Ekwueme (2022), Adeyemi and Adebayo (2023), Ly, et al (2020) and Cumming et al. (2016). However, none of these studies used agricultural credit, agricultural development assistance, road transport, information and communication technology, and institutional quality as determinants of food security in the model. Some of these works used other methodologies or were conducted in foreign economies, making their findings not very relevant for Nigeria due to differences in macroeconomic indicators. Furthermore, the data generating process in Nigeria from which these specific realizations of time series values are collected are constantly changing. This makes it expedient to evaluate how entrepreneurial sustainability determines food security in Nigeria.

1.1 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to evaluate the relationship between entrepreneurial sustainability and food security in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- (i) Examine the relationship between agricultural credit and food security in Nigeria.
- (ii) Evaluate the relationship between agricultural development assistance and food security in Nigeria.
- (iii) Analyze the relationship between road transport and food security in Nigeria.
- (iv) Determine the relationship between information and communication technology and food security in Nigeria.
- (v) Analyze the relationship between institutional quality and food security in Nigeria.

1.2 Hypothesis

The hypotheses of this study are:

Ho₁: Agricultural credit has no significant effect on food security in Nigeria.

Ho₂: Agricultural development assistance has no significant effect on food security in Nigeria.

Ho₃: Road transport has no significant effect on food security in Nigeria.

Ho₄: Information and communication technology have no effect on food security in Nigeria.

Ho₅: Institutional quality has no significant effect on food security in Nigeria.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Entrepreneurial Sustainability

Esubalew and Adebisi (2024) described entrepreneurial sustainability as the practice of starting and operating a business with the aim of maximizing social benefits accruing to the society, ensuring long term economic viability while minimizing to the lowest extent, negative effects on the environment. It also involves integrating sustainability principles into all aspects of an entrepreneurial venture such that the business adds value to society while generating profit for itself.

2.2 Food Security in Nigeria

According to Owoade (2017), food security could be conceptualized as the situation where everyone has sufficient safe and healthy food to eat. Food security has four major parts: having sufficient food to cater for your needs for a specific period of time, the effective demand to purchase food in the market place, eating the proper balanced diet, having it sufficient to take you for a reasonable period of time (Ogunyinka & Ekwueme, 2022). Food insecurity is associated with poverty and could be caused by political problems, leading to hunger and poor nutrition. There is need for the government to ensure food security by integrating local, national and global perspectives into policy making

2.3 Empirical Review

The work of Adeyemi and Adebayo (2023) explored the role of access to finance in promoting sustainable entrepreneurship and its subsequent impact on food security and economic growth. The study adopted the time series research design and used econometric techniques to analyze the relationship between the exogenous and

endogenous variables. The findings showed that improved access to finance for entrepreneurs, particularly in the agricultural sector, led to increased investment in sustainable practices, enhanced food security, and contributed to economic growth. The study recommended expanding financial inclusion and developing tailored financial products for sustainable businesses.

An empirical study was conducted by Oladimeji et al. (2023) on the effects of climate change on food security in Nigeria and the role of sustainable agricultural practices in mitigating these effects. The specific objectives included to evaluate effects of climate resilient farming practices, determine effects of agro-forestry on food security in Nigeria, and evaluate the effect of improved food security outcomes on climate change. The study found that climate-resilient farming practices, such as agroforestry and conservation agriculture, improved food security outcomes by enhancing agricultural productivity and resilience to climate shocks.

The empirical work of Eze and Nwosu (2022) proposed an integrated framework linking entrepreneurial sustainability, food security, and economic growth. The findings indicated that sustainable agricultural entrepreneurship enhances food security, which in turn supports economic growth by creating a healthy and productive workforce. The study emphasized the need for multi-sectoral policies and collaborations to achieve sustainable development goals. A study by Ogunyinka and Ekwueme (2022) also explored the role of agricultural entrepreneurship in enhancing food security in Nigeria. The findings showed that agricultural entrepreneurs who implemented innovative farming techniques and engaged in value-added processing significantly contributed to food availability and reduced post-harvest losses. The study recommended targeted interventions to support agricultural entrepreneurs through training and access to finance in order to improve food security.

A study conducted by Onugu and Ebitu (2021) identified key challenges faced by entrepreneurs in adopting sustainable practices, including high costs, lack of awareness, and inadequate regulatory support. It also highlighted opportunities such as the growing market for green products and the potential for public-private partnerships to support sustainable business initiatives. Okoye and Onyeka (2021) assessed the contribution of small and medium scale enterprises to economic growth in Nigeria, focusing on the non-oil sectors. The study adopted the ex post facto research design and used the OLS methodology for analysis. The findings indicated that SMEs are crucial drivers of economic diversification and employment creation. The study recommended policies to improve the business environment, enhance access to finance, and provide capacity-building programs for SMEs.

Akinwale and Adepoju (2020) analyzed the impact of sustainable business practices on the performance of SMEs in Nigeria. The findings indicated that SMEs

adopting sustainable practices experienced higher profitability and growth rates compared to those that did not. The study emphasized the role of government support and access to green finance in promoting sustainability among SMEs.

Ly, et al (2020) in a study, examined foreign trade on food security in ten Southeast Asian nations between 2000 and 2015, using panel data. The study used fixed effects model (FE), random effects model (RE), and feasible generalized least squares model (FGLS) for its analysis as the Hausman specification test showed that the fixed effects model is more reliable. The results revealed a positive relationship between international trade and food security in the study. However, other exogenous variables like inflation, agricultural productivity, and share of agricultural land over total land area had significant effects on food security in Southeast Asian countries. Based on the results, the study recommended a reduction of trade barriers and more government support for trade liberalization among the countries of study.

In Nigeria, Eze et al. (2017) examined the synergistic effects of entrepreneurship and agricultural development on economic growth. The study concluded that fostering sustainable business practices in agriculture not only improves food security but also drives overall economic development. A similar study by Cumming et al. (2016) proposed an integrated framework linking entrepreneurial sustainability, food security, and economic growth. The study found that sustainable entrepreneurship in agriculture leads to improved food security, which in turn supports economic growth by creating a healthy and productive workforce. Furthermore, Okpara (2011) found that sustainable practices in agriculture, such as organic farming and efficient resource use can enhance food security and environmental sustainability. The study called for supportive policies to encourage sustainable agricultural entrepreneurship.

2.4 Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework that underpins the study is the endogenous growth and institutional theory, which provides a foundational understanding of the relationships between entrepreneurial sustainability, food security, and economic growth in Nigeria. Endogenous growth theory posits that economic growth is driven by factors such as innovation, human capital development, and technological progress. Sustainable entrepreneurship contributes to economic growth by fostering innovation in green technologies, creating new markets, and improving productivity (Romer, 1990). This assertion is supported by the institutional theory which posits that entrepreneurial behavior is shaped by sustainability practices through regulatory frameworks, norms and values Sustainable entrepreneurs in Nigeria navigate institutional pressure by adopting practices that align with societal expectations and regulatory requirement in ensuring that entrepreneurial sustainability, food security and economic growth are attained (Scott, 1995). In with this theoretical framework, model specifications are built to support the objectives of the study.

3. MODEL SPECIFICATION

Given that Y_{it} is food security determined by X_{it} , a simple model of sustainable growth is stated as in equation 1.

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \sum_{k=1}^j \beta_k X_{kit} + u_{it}; \quad k = 1, \dots, j \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

The time series effects is equation (2) below

$$u_{it} = \varphi_i + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

The study adapted Ly, et al's (2020) model that examines the impact of foreign trade on food security in ten Southeast Asian nations between 2000 and 2015. The functional form of the model is stated as equation 3 below

$$FS_{it} = F (TO, GDPC, APRO, RURALP, ARLA, POPG, INF) \quad (3)$$

Where;

FS_{it} = food security, represented by three indicators: *availability, stability, and accessibility* at country i year t.

TO_{it} = trade Openness captured as the proportion of the total trade to GDP of country i year

$GDPC_{it}$ = GDP per capita of country i year t]

ARL_{it} = proportion of agricultural land over the total land area of country i year t

$POPG_{it}$ = growth rate of the population for country i year t

$RURALP_{it}$ = number of farmers as a percentage of the total population of country i year t.

$APRO_{it}$ = agricultural productivity of country i year t.

INF_{it} = inflation of country i year t.

This model was modified from a previous study as trade openness was replaced with entrepreneurial sustainability. The model adopted for the study added agricultural credit, agricultural development assistance from government and non-government organization, effective road transport, the use of technology to, institutional framework, and agricultural output as control variables.

The model of this study is:

$$FS_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ESt + \beta_2 ACT + \beta_3 ADAt + \beta_4 ICTt + \beta_5 RTt + \beta_6 RQt + vt \dots \dots \dots 4$$

By assuming linearity among the variables and taking the natural logarithm of both sides of equation (3), one can obtain:

$$FS_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 LESt + \beta_2 LACT + \beta_3 LADAt + \beta_4 LICt + \beta_5 LRTt + \beta_6 LRQt + vt \dots \dots \dots 5$$

Where:

LFS_t = Food Security at time t (dependent Variable)

Others are the independent Variables, explained below:

LES_t = Entrepreneurial Sustainability at time t

LAC_t = Agricultural Credit at time t

$LADA_t$ = agricultural development assistance at time t

LRT_t = Road Transport at time t

$LICT_t$ = Information and Communication Technology at time t

LRQ_t = Regulatory Quality

v_t = Error term

Definition of Variable

Dependent Variables – One-Sector Model.

Food Security (LFS): Measured by food availability, which can be proxied by food production index.

Independent Variable

Entrepreneurial Sustainability (ES): Proxied by the number of sustainable businesses or SMEs, access to finance for entrepreneurs, and the implementation of sustainable business practices.

Agricultural Credit (LAC): Measured by the volume of loans to SMEs and entrepreneurs, interest rates, and availability of microfinance.

Agricultural Development Assistance (LADA): Proxied as organizations that support investment to rural farmers

Road Infrastructure (RT): Proxied by the quality and availability of infrastructure, such as transportation.

Information and Technological Technology (ICT): Proxied by the adoption rate of digital tools and agricultural technologies.

Regulatory Quality (RQ): Measured by the ease of doing business score and regulatory quality index.

Sources and Method of Data Collection

This research work used secondary data. Secondary data involves the use of existing data collected for purposes other than the current research. The data are from Central Bank of Nigeria, National Bureau of Statistics, World Bank, Food and Agriculture Organization and United Nations Development Programme.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section discusses results elicited from the empirical examination of entrepreneurial sustainability, food Security and economic growth in Nigeria.

Table 1

Summary Statistics

Statistic	LFS	LES	LAC	LADA	LRT	LICT	LRQ
Mean	120.5581	40.99737	2281.401	15.35338	1053.553	7587.608	18.60212
Median	119.0000	41.17215	2426.535	2.735488	727.8074	6823.141	18.13725
Maximum	127.0000	62.04167	2679.554	121.5523	2727.535	21151.67	27.01422
Minimum	115.0000	30.40000	1508.554	0.102989	181.4911	255.1983	8.457711
Std. Dev.	3.958429	6.819279	325.6934	28.70963	835.0735	6183.147	5.345538
Skewness	0.318043	0.604758	0.782393	2.205553	0.817067	0.455566	0.039614
Kurtosis	1.907569	3.698751	2.421792	6.995480	2.219969	2.054851	1.866779
Jarque- Bera	2.863103	3.495867	4.985994	63.46390	5.874591	3.087882	2.312088
Probability	0.238938	0.174133	0.082662	0.000000	0.053009	0.213538	0.314729
Observatio n	43	43	43	43	43	43	43

Source: Extract from E-views 9 Output, 2024

Table 1 describes the properties of the data for the estimated time series. It is observed that all variables have positive mean, minimum and maximum values. The standard deviations of the variables are mostly low with the exception of road transport and information and communication technology. Moreover, while all variables are positively skewed, agricultural development assistance is not normally distributed.

Table 2

Unit Root Test

Variable	Coefficient	Prob.	Coefficient	Prob.	I(d)
Phillip-Peron (PP)					
	LEVEL		FIRST DIFFERENCE		
LFS	0.7181	0.3996	1.9889**	0.0458	I(1)
LES	0.1772	0.9335	3.8734***	0.0048	I(1)
LAC	2.5233	0.1173	2.9628**	0.0470	I(1)
LADA	1.1956	0.6676	3.9411***	0.0040	I(1)
LRT	1.2439	0.6464	3.5725***	0.0108	I(1)
LICT	3.2722	0.0227**	3.4928***	0.0132	I(0)
LRQ	1.5983	0.4747	4.0490***	0.0030	I(1)

Source: Extract from E-views 9 Output, 2024

NB: ***, ** and * indicate significance at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

Table 2 presents unit root stationarity test of the variables employed in this study using the conventional Phillip-Peron test. Considering the level and differenced equations, the results show a mixed order of integration where LICT is stationary at level while LFS, LES, LAC, LADA, LRT and LRQ became stationary after taking their first difference.

Table 3

ARDL Bound Test

Bound Cointegration Test			
F-Statistic	I(0)	I(1)	Significance
32.4194***	2.12	3.23	10%
	2.45	3.61	5%
	3.15	4.43	1%

Source: Extract from E-views 9 Output, 2024

NB: ***, ** and * indicate significance at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

It is observed in Table 3 that the F-statistic is greater than the critical values at upper bound (3.61) at 5% level of significance. This informs the rejection of the null hypothesis at 5% level of significance and the conclusion that variables are co-integrated. In other words, there is a long run co-integrating relationship among variables employed. Existence of co-integration necessitates the interest in the error correction components of the models.

Table 4
ARDL Estimation

Summary of Long Run and Short Run Estimation			
Panel A: Long Run			
Variable	Coefficient	t-statistic	Prob.
C	4.9109***	0.3863	0.0002
LES	0.2406***	0.0840	0.0459
LAC	-0.0616***	0.0105	0.0043
LADA	-0.0166***	0.0050	0.0294
LRT	-0.0804***	0.0246	0.0308
LICT	0.0934***	0.0200	0.0096
LRQ	-0.1049***	0.0147	0.0021
Panel B: Short Run			
D(LES)	-0.0043	0.0032	0.2602
D(LES(-1))	-0.0136	0.0067	0.1119
D(LES(-2))	-0.0160***	0.0058	0.0532
D(LES(-3))	-0.0599***	0.0142	0.0136
D(LAC)	-0.0108	0.0051	0.1050
D(LAC(-1))	-0.0107	0.0059	0.1437
D(LAC(-2))	-0.0000	0.0058	0.9898
D(LAC(-3))	0.0220***	0.0054	0.0159
D(LADA)	-0.0047***	0.0007	0.0033
D(LADA(-1))	0.0003	0.0018	0.8547
D(LADA(-2))	0.0000	0.0004	0.8562
D(LADA(-3))	-0.0020	0.0017	0.3138
D(LRT)	0.0211	0.0248	0.4431
D(LRT(-1))	-0.0050	0.0223	0.8337
D(LRT(-2))	-0.0065	0.0141	0.6671
D(LRT(-3))	0.0423***	0.0070	0.0038
D(LICT)	-0.0094	0.0142	0.5441
D(LICT(-1))	-0.0447***	0.0090	0.0076
D(LICT(-2))	0.0002	0.0043	0.9839
D(LICT(-3))	0.0114	0.0092	0.2835
D(LRQ)	-0.0004	0.0022	0.8468
D(LNRQ(-1))	0.0026	0.0102	0.8052
D(LNRQ(-2))	0.0067	0.0033	0.1147
D(LNRQ(-3))	0.0304***	0.0042	0.0020
ECT(-1)	-0.3712***	0.0921	0.0157

Source: Extract from *E-views 9 Output, 2024*

NB: ***, ** and * indicate significance at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

The long run results as seen in panel A of table 4 shows that holding other explanatory variables constant, there is a positive long run relationship between Entrepreneurial Sustainability (LES) and Food Security (LFS); and this is supported with (Cumming et al. 2016; Eze & Nwosu 2022). This implies that a unit change in entrepreneurial sustainability increases food security by 0.2406 in the long run; on average, holding other things constant, at 5% level of statistical significance. Conversely, there is a negative long run relationship between Agricultural Credit (LAC) and Food Security (LFS).

This implies that a unit change in agricultural credit (LAC) decreases food security (LFS) by 0.0616 in the long run, on average, holding other things constant, at 1% level of statistical significance. The impact of agricultural development assistance on food security is also negative as a unit change in LADA decreases FS by 0.0166 in the long run, on average, holding other things constant, at 5% level of statistical significance. Moreso, other variables including road transportation (LRT) and regulatory quality (LRQ) also impact negatively on food security by 0.0804 and 0.1049 respectively, while information and communication technology (LICT) impact positively on food security (FS) by 0.0934, in the long run, on average, holding other things constant. The impacts of all the three variables are statistically significant.

From the short run regression results on panel B of table 4, it is seen that all explanatory variables have significant impact on food security, though at different lags which suggests that lag dependency is important for the short run relationship between food security and explanatory variables considered in the regression model. Specifically, while entrepreneurial sustainability has negative short run impact on food security at second and third lags, agricultural credit has positive short run impact on food security. Moreover, the level value of agricultural development assistance is seen to impact negatively on food security, while the differenced values of road transportation, and of information and communication technology also impact negatively on food security. The lag of regulatory quality has statistically significant positive impact on food security in the short run.

The error correction coefficient parameter is -0.37 which indicates that 37% errors generated in one period is corrected in the next period. This highly significant and negative ECT coefficient also supports evidence that there is a stable long-run relationship between the economic growth and its predictors considered in the regression model.

Table 5

Post Estimation Diagnostics

Post Estimation Test (Robustness Check)			
Diagnostic Test	F-statistic	Df	Prob.
Panel A: Primary Diagnostics			
R ²	0.8199	-	
Adj R ²	0.8096	-	
DW	2.3790	-	
F-Stat	296.6401***	-	0.0000
Panel B: Secondary Diagnostics			
Linearity (RESET)	0.8584	1, 14	0.4075
Serial Correlation	14.9017	2, 2	0.0629
Heteroscedasticity	0.5640	34,4	0.8429
JB-Normality	5.4832	-	0.0644

Source: Extract from E-views 9 Output, 2024

NB: ***, ** and * indicate significance at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively.

The summary of primary and secondary diagnostics is reported on table 5. From panel A, the adjusted R² revealed that 80% of the variation in economic growth is jointly explained by explanatory variables employed in the regression model which indicates the goodness of fit of the regression model. The Durbin Watson statistic suggests the absence of first-order serial correlation in the regression model. Moreover, the F-statistic indicates that the model is adequately specified. On panel B, considering further estimation tests of reliability of the regression model at 5% level of significance, results revealed that there is absence of specification error, second-order serial correlation and heteroscedasticity, with normally distributed residuals.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study concludes that entrepreneurial sustainability has a great influence on enhancing food security in the Nigerian economy. This importance is demonstrated in the proportion of the population engaged in agro-allied businesses in the economy. The study therefore recommends that government should strategize and partner with the private sector in funding agricultural production, and creating a good road transport network in Nigeria. The government should also invest in information and communications technology, and provide policies that will enhance institutional quality in Nigeria.

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